

Finite frequency H_∞ control design for nonlinear systems

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ABSTRACT

The work deals finite frequency H_∞ control design for continuous time nonlinear systems, we provide sufficient conditions, ensuring that the closed-loop model is stable. Simulations will be gifted to show level of attenuation that a H_∞ lower can be by our method obtained developed where further comparison.

Keywords:

Finite frequency

LMIs

Nonlinear systems

T-S Model

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fuzzy models [1] it generated widespread interest from engineers, mainly for renowned T-S systems my actually approach great category for non linear models. Then, the T-S systems is its universal approximation of a smooth non linear function by a family of IF and THEN non linear rules that represent the output/ input relationships of the models [2]-[11].

The interest of the literature mentioned above the H_∞ control design in the FF range. whereas, in such cases, standard design methods of full frequency range can provide conservatism. Nevertheless, in an actual application, the design characteristics are generally given in selector Frequency domains (see, [12]-[21]).

In this work, we develop new our method concerning FF design of nonlinear continuous systems. Us- ing theadequate conditions are developed, ensuring that the closed loop system is stable. Numerical examples are provides to prove the effectiveness of FF propose method. **Notations :**

- $*$: Form symmetry
- $Q > 0$: Form positive
- $\text{sym}(M) > 0$: $M + M^*$
- I : form Identity
- $\text{diag}\{..\}$: Block diagonal form

2. T-S MODELS

Let's the continuous model is given by

$$\dot{x}(t) = \frac{\sum_{r=1}^n \sigma_r(t)(A_r x(t) + L_r u(t) + B_r v(t))}{\sum_{r=1}^n \sigma_r(t)}, y(t) = \frac{\sum_{r=1}^n \sigma_r(t)(C_r x(t) + E_r u(t) + D_r v(t))}{\sum_{r=1}^n \sigma_r(t)} \quad (1)$$

with

$$\lambda_r(t) = \prod_{j=1}^p N_{r_s}(\mu_s(t))$$

and

$$\sigma_r = \frac{\lambda_r(t)}{\sum_{r=1}^n \lambda_r(t)}; \quad 0 \leq \lambda_r \leq 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{r=1}^n \lambda_r = 1 \quad (2)$$

and $\sigma = [\sigma_1, \dots, \sigma_r]^*$, the T-S system can be rewritten as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= A(\sigma)x(t) + L(\sigma)u(t) + B(\sigma)v(t) \\ y(t) &= C(\sigma)x(t) + E(\sigma)u(t) + D(\sigma)v(t) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where

$$\{A(\sigma); B(\sigma); L(\sigma); B(\sigma); C(\sigma); E(\sigma); D(\sigma)\} = \sum_{r=1}^n \rho_r(t) \{A_r; L_r; B_r; C_r; E_r; D_r\} \quad (4)$$

3. PDC CONTROLLER SCHEME

The fuzzy control as follows:

$$u(t) = \sum_{s=1}^n \sigma_s K_s x(t) \quad (5)$$

then, we have the closed loop model:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= A_c(\lambda)x(t) + B(\lambda)v(t) \\ y(t) &= C_c(\lambda)x(t) + D(\lambda)v(t) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

with

$$A_c(\sigma) = A_c(\sigma) + L(\sigma)K(\sigma); \quad c(\sigma) = C_c(\sigma) + E(\sigma)K(\sigma) \quad (7)$$

problem formulation Given: the state feedback in the form of (5) such that:

$$\int_{\mu \in \nabla} Y^*(\mu)Y(\mu)d\mu \leq \gamma^2 \int_{\mu \in \nabla} V^*(\mu)V(\mu)d\mu \quad (8)$$

with Δ is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Different frequency ranges

	Low frequency	Middle frequency	High frequency
∇	$ \mu \leq \bar{\mu}_l$	$\bar{\mu}_1 \leq \mu \leq \bar{\mu}_2$	$ \mu \geq \bar{\mu}_h$
Π	$\begin{bmatrix} -S(\sigma) & R(\sigma) \\ R(\sigma) & \bar{\mu}_l^2 S \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} -S(\sigma) & R(\sigma) + j\bar{\mu}_0 S(\sigma) \\ R(\sigma) - j\bar{\mu}_0 S(\sigma) & -\bar{\mu}_1 \bar{\mu}_2 R \end{bmatrix}$	$\begin{bmatrix} S(\sigma) & R(\sigma) \\ R(\sigma) & -\bar{\mu}_h^2 S(\sigma) \end{bmatrix}$

4. MAIN RESULTS

4.1. Useful lemma

Lemma 4.1 Tuan, H. D *et al.*[22] If the following conditions are met:

$$\Omega_{rr} < 0 \quad 1 \leq r \leq n \frac{1}{n-1} \Omega_{rr} + \frac{1}{2} [\Omega_{rs} + \Omega_{sr}] < 0; \quad 1 \leq r \neq s \leq n \quad (9)$$

and

$$\sum_{r=1}^n \sum_{s=1}^n \lambda_r \lambda_s \Omega_{rs} < 0 \quad (10)$$

Lemma 4.2 El-Amrani, A. *et al.* [23]. Let $\mathcal{T} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathcal{M} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, so that the following conditions are equivalent:

1. $\mathcal{M}^{\perp*} \mathcal{T} \mathcal{M}^{\perp} < 0$
2. $\exists \mathcal{N} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times m} : \mathcal{T} + \text{sym}[\mathcal{M}\mathcal{N}] < 0$

Lemma 4.3 Closed loop (6) is stable, if $R(\sigma) = R(\sigma)^* \in \mathbb{H}_n, 0 < S = S^* \in \mathbb{H}_n$ such that

$$\begin{pmatrix} A_c(\sigma) & B(\sigma) \\ I & 0 \end{pmatrix}^* \Pi \begin{pmatrix} A_c(\sigma) & B(\sigma) \\ I & 0 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} C_c^T(\sigma)C_c(\sigma) & C_c^T(\sigma)D(\sigma) \\ D^T(\sigma)C_c(\sigma) & D^T(\sigma)D(\sigma) - \gamma^2 I \end{pmatrix} < 0 \quad (11)$$

with Π is given of Table 1.

4.2. Finite frequency analysis

Theorem 4.4 The fuzzy model (6) is stable, if $R(\sigma) \in \mathbb{H}_n, 0 < S \in \mathbb{H}_n, 0 < W(\sigma) \in \mathbb{H}_n, Z(\sigma) \in \mathbb{H}_n, H(\sigma) \in \mathbb{H}_n$ such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\text{sym}[Z(\sigma)] & W(\sigma) + Z(\sigma)A(\sigma) - H^*(\sigma) \\ \star & \text{sym}[H(\sigma)A_c(\sigma)] \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Psi_{11}(\sigma) & \Psi_{12}(\sigma) + Z(\sigma)A_c(\sigma) - H^*(\sigma) & Z(\sigma)B(\sigma) & 0 \\ \star & \Psi_{22}(\sigma) + \text{sym}[H(\sigma)A_c(\sigma)] & H(\sigma)B(\sigma) & C_c^*(\sigma) \\ \star & \star & -\gamma^2 I & D^*(\sigma) \\ \star & \star & \star & -I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (13)$$

- Low frequency (LF) range:

$$\Psi_{11}(\sigma) = -S(\sigma) - Z(\sigma) - Z^*(\sigma); \quad \Psi_{12}(\sigma) = R(\sigma); \quad \Psi_{22}(\sigma) = \bar{\mu}_l^2 S(\sigma) \quad (14)$$

- Middle frequency range (MF) range:

$$\Psi_{11} = -S(\sigma) - Z(\sigma) - Z^*(\sigma); \quad \Psi_{12} = R(\sigma) + j\bar{\mu}_0 S(\sigma); \quad \Psi_{22} = -\bar{\mu}_1 \bar{\mu}_2 S(\sigma) \quad (15)$$

- High frequency (HF) range:

$$\Psi_{11}(\sigma) = S(\sigma) - Z(\sigma) - Z^*(\sigma); \quad \Psi_{12}(\sigma) = R(\sigma); \quad \Psi_{22}(\sigma) = -\bar{\mu}_h^2 S(\sigma)$$

Proof 4.5 Let $\bar{A}(\sigma), W(\sigma) = W(\sigma)^* > 0$ such that

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_c(\sigma) \\ I \end{bmatrix}^* \begin{bmatrix} 0 & W(\sigma) \\ W(\sigma) & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_c(\sigma) \\ I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (16)$$

define:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & W(\sigma) \\ W(\sigma) & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathcal{N} = \begin{bmatrix} Z(\sigma) \\ H(\sigma) \end{bmatrix}; \\ \mathcal{M} &= [-I \quad A_c(\sigma)]; \quad \mathcal{M}^{\perp} = \begin{bmatrix} A_c(\sigma) \\ I \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

let lemma 4.1., (16) and (17) are equivalent to:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & W(\sigma) \\ W(\sigma) & 0 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} Z(\sigma) \\ H(\sigma) \end{bmatrix} [-I \quad A_c(\sigma)] + [-I \quad A_c(\sigma)]^* \begin{bmatrix} Z(\sigma) \\ H(\sigma) \end{bmatrix}^* < 0 \quad (18)$$

which is nothing but (12), let LF case :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T} &= \begin{bmatrix} -S & R(\sigma) & 0 \\ \star & \bar{\mu}_l^2 S + C_c^*(\sigma)C_c(\sigma) & C_c^*(\sigma)D(\sigma) \\ \star & \star & -\gamma^2 I + D^*(\sigma)D(\sigma) \end{bmatrix}; \\ \mathcal{M}^{\perp} &= \begin{bmatrix} A_c(\sigma) & B(\sigma) \\ I & 0 \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}; \quad \mathcal{M} = [-I \quad A_c(\sigma) \quad B(\sigma)]; \\ \mathcal{N} &= [Z(\sigma)^T \quad H(\sigma)^T \quad 0]^T \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

we have

$$\mathcal{T} + \text{sym}(\mathcal{N}\mathcal{M}) < 0 \quad (20)$$

using Lemma 4.1., we obtain (11).

4.3. Finite frequency design

Theorem 4.6 The fuzzy model (6) is stable, if $\tilde{R}(\sigma) \in \mathbb{H}_n$, $0 < \tilde{S} \in \mathbb{H}_n$, $0 < \tilde{W}(\sigma) \in \mathbb{H}_n$, $G(\sigma)$, $\bar{Z}(\sigma)$ such that:

$$\begin{bmatrix} -\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) - \bar{Z}(\sigma) & \tilde{W}(\sigma) + A(\sigma)\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) + B(\sigma)G^*(\sigma) - \beta\bar{Z}(\sigma) \\ \star & \text{sym}[\beta(A(\sigma)\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) + B(\sigma)G^*(\sigma))] \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{\Psi}_{11}(\sigma) & \bar{\Psi}_{12}(\sigma) & B(\sigma) & 0 \\ \star & \bar{\Psi}_{22}(\sigma) & \beta B(\sigma) & \bar{Z}(\sigma)C^*(\sigma) + G(\sigma)E^*(\sigma) \\ \star & \star & -\gamma^2 I & D^*(\sigma) \\ \star & \star & \star & -I \end{bmatrix} < 0 \quad (22)$$

- $|\mu| \leq \bar{\mu}_l$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Psi}_{11}(\sigma) &= -\tilde{S}(\sigma) - \bar{Z}^*(\sigma) - \bar{Z}(\sigma); \\ \bar{\Psi}_{22}(\sigma) &= \bar{\mu}_l^2 \tilde{S}(\sigma) + \text{sym}[\beta(A(\sigma)\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) + B(\sigma)G^*(\sigma))]; \\ \bar{\Psi}_{12}(\sigma) &= \tilde{R}(\sigma) - \beta\bar{Z}(\sigma) + A(\sigma)\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) + B(\sigma)G^*(\sigma). \end{aligned}$$

- $\bar{\mu}_1 \leq \mu \leq \bar{\mu}_2$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Psi}_{11}(\sigma) &= -\tilde{S}(\sigma) - \bar{Z}^*(\sigma) - \bar{Z}(\sigma); \\ \bar{\Psi}_{22}(\sigma) &= -\bar{\mu}_1 \bar{\mu}_2 \tilde{S}(\sigma) + \text{sym}[\beta(A(\sigma)\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) + B(\sigma)G^*(\sigma))]; \\ \bar{\Psi}_{12}(\sigma) &= \tilde{R}(\sigma) + j\bar{\mu}_0 \tilde{S}(\sigma) - \beta\bar{Z}(\sigma) + A(\sigma)\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) + B(\sigma)G^*(\sigma) \end{aligned}$$

- $|\mu| \geq \bar{\mu}_h$

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\Psi}_{11}(\sigma) &= \tilde{S}(\sigma) - \bar{Z}^*(\sigma) - \bar{Z}(\sigma); \\ \bar{\Psi}_{12}(\sigma) &= \tilde{R}(\sigma) - \beta\bar{Z}(\sigma) + A(\sigma)\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) + B(\sigma)G^*(\sigma); \\ \bar{\Psi}_{22}(\sigma) &= -\bar{\mu}_h^2 \tilde{S}(\sigma) + \text{sym}[\beta(A(\sigma)\bar{Z}^*(\sigma) + B(\sigma)G^*(\sigma))]. \end{aligned}$$

therefore :

$$K(\sigma) = (\bar{Z}^{-1}(\sigma)G(\sigma))^* \quad (23)$$

Proof 4.7 First, for matrix variable $H(\sigma)$ in theorem 4.2., let $H(\sigma) = \beta Z(\sigma)$, after that by replacing (7) into (12) and (13), respectively, moreover, let,

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{Z}(\sigma) &= Z^{-1}(\sigma); \quad G(\sigma) = \bar{Z}(\sigma)K^*; \quad \tilde{S}(\sigma) = Z^{-1}(\sigma)S(\sigma)Z^{-*}(\sigma); \\ \tilde{R}(\sigma) &= Z^{-1}(\sigma)R(\sigma)Z^{-*}(\sigma); \quad \tilde{W}(\sigma) = Z^{-1}(\sigma)W(\sigma)Z^{-*}(\sigma) \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying (12) by $\text{diag}\{Z^{-1}(\sigma), Z^{-1}(\sigma)\}$, and (13) by $\text{diag}\{Z^{-1}(\sigma), Z^{-1}(\sigma), I, I\}$, we have (12) and (13) are equivalent (21) and (22), respectively. **Theorem 4.8** The fuzzy model (6) is stable. If $R_r \in \mathbb{H}_n$, $0 < S \in \mathbb{H}_n$, $0 < W_r \in \mathbb{H}_n$, $\bar{Z}_s, G_s$ such that

$$\tilde{\Psi}_{rr} < 0; \quad \tilde{\Upsilon}_{rr} < 0; \quad 1 \leq r \leq n \quad (24)$$

$$\frac{1}{r-1} \tilde{\Psi}_{rr} + \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{\Psi}_{rs} + \tilde{\Psi}_{sr}] < 0; \quad 1 \leq r \neq s \leq n \quad (25)$$

$$\frac{1}{r-1} \tilde{\Upsilon}_{rr} + \frac{1}{2} [\tilde{\Upsilon}_{rs} + \tilde{\Upsilon}_{sr}] < 0; \quad 1 \leq r \neq s \leq n \quad (26)$$

where

$$\tilde{\Psi}_{rs} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{\Psi}_{11rs} & \tilde{\Psi}_{12rs} & B_r & 0 \\ \star & \tilde{\Psi}_{22rs} & \beta B_r & \bar{F}_s C_r^* + G_s E_r^* \\ \star & \star & -\gamma^2 I & D_r^* \\ \star & \star & \star & -I \end{bmatrix};$$

$$\tilde{\Upsilon}_{rs} = \begin{bmatrix} -\bar{Z}_s^* - \bar{Z}_s & W_r + A_r \bar{Z}_s^* + B_r G_s^* - \beta \bar{Z}_s \\ \star & sym[\beta(A_r \bar{Z}_s^* + B_r G_s^*)] \end{bmatrix}$$

- $|\mu| \leq \bar{\mu}_l$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Psi}_{11rs} &= -\tilde{S}_s - \bar{Z}_s^* - \bar{Z}_s; \\ \tilde{\Psi}_{12rs} &= \tilde{R}_r - \beta \bar{Z}_s + A_r \bar{Z}_s^* + B_r G_s^*; \\ \tilde{\Psi}_{22rs} &= \bar{\mu}_l^2 \tilde{S}_s + sym[\beta(A_r \bar{Z}_s^* + B_r G_s^*)]. \end{aligned}$$

- $\bar{\mu}_1 \leq \mu \leq \bar{\mu}_2$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Psi}_{11rs} &= -\tilde{S}_s - \bar{Z}_s^* - \bar{Z}_s; \\ \tilde{\Psi}_{12rs} &= \tilde{R}_r + j\bar{\mu}_0 \tilde{S}_s - \beta \bar{U}_s + A_r \bar{Z}_s^* + B_r G_s^*; \\ \tilde{\Psi}_{22rs} &= -\bar{\mu}_1 \bar{\mu}_2 \tilde{S}_s + sym[\beta(A_r \bar{Z}_s^* + B_r G_s^*)]. \end{aligned}$$

- $|\mu| \geq \bar{\mu}_h$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\Psi}_{11rs} &= \tilde{S}_s - \bar{Z}_s^* - \bar{Z}_s; \\ \tilde{\Psi}_{12rs} &= \tilde{R}_r - \beta \bar{Z}_s + A_r \bar{Z}_s^* + B_r G_s^*; \\ \tilde{\Psi}_{22rs} &= -\bar{\mu}_h^2 \tilde{S}_s + sym[\beta(A_r \bar{Z}_s^* + B_r G_s^*)]. \end{aligned}$$

The matrices gains are obtained by:

$$K_s = (\bar{Z}_s^{-1} G_s)^*, \quad 1 \leq s \leq n \tag{27}$$

Proof 4.9 by applying the Lemma 4.1., we have Theorem 4.3.

5. SIMULATIONS

5.1. Example 1

Consider fuzzy system (3) with two rules [24]:

$$\begin{aligned} A_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 17.2941 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \quad A_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 12.6305 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \\ E_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -0.1765 \end{bmatrix}; \quad L_1 = L_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1 \\ 0.1 \end{bmatrix}; \\ E_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ -0.0779 \end{bmatrix}; \quad B_1 = B_2 = 0.1; \\ C_1 = C_2 &= [1 \quad 1]; \quad D_1 = D_2 = 0 \end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} N_2(x_1) &= \left(\frac{1}{1 + \exp(-7(x_1 - \frac{\pi}{4}))} \right) \left(\frac{1}{1 + \exp(-7(x_1 + \frac{\pi}{4}))} \right); \\ N_1(x_1) &= 1 - N_2(x_1). \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

let

$$v(t) = \begin{cases} 2 & 2 \leq t \leq 3 \\ 2 & 5 \leq t \leq 6 \\ 0 & \text{others} \end{cases} \tag{30}$$

We propose in table 2 shows the values of γ obtained in different frequency ranges. By Theorem 4.3., the controller gains are given by:

- Low frequency (LF) range (with $\beta_1 = 0.0502$ and $\gamma = 0.2507$):

$$K_1 = [168.2205 \quad 22.9439]; \quad K_2 = [353.5002 \quad 115.2592] \tag{31}$$

- Middle frequency (MF) range (with $\beta_1 = 0.5025$ and $\gamma = 0.8355$):

$$K_1 = [186.8988 \quad 36.1978]; \quad K_2 = [378.9459 \quad 109.7698] \quad (32)$$

- High frequency (HF) range (with $\beta_1 = 0.2478$ and $\gamma = 0.5702$):

$$K_1 = [203.4092 \quad 43.1392]; \quad K_2 = [356.0428 \quad 101.8833] \quad (33)$$

Table 2. Obtained γ by different domains

Frequency ranges	methods	γ
EF ($0 \leq \mu \leq \infty$)	[16]	Infeasible
EF ($0 \leq \mu \leq \infty$)	Theorem 4.3. ($\tilde{S}_s = 0$)	1.1789
LF ($ \mu \leq 0.7$)	<i>Theorem 2 in [16]</i>	1.3598
LF ($ \mu \leq 0.7$)	Theorem 4.3.	0.2507
MF ($1 \leq \mu \leq 5$)	<i>Corollary 1 in [16]</i>	1.3010
MF ($1 \leq \mu \leq 5$)	Theorem 4.3.	0.8355
HF ($ \mu \geq 6$)	<i>Corollary 2 in [16]</i>	-
HF ($ \mu \geq 6$)	Theorem 4.3.	0.5702
MF ($628 \leq \mu \leq 6283$)	<i>Corollary 1 in [16]</i>	1.5786
MF ($628 \leq \mu \leq 6283$)	Theorem 4.3.	0.9245
HF ($ \mu \geq 6283$)	<i>Corollary 2 in [16]</i>	-
HF ($ \mu \geq 6283$)	Theorem 4.3.	0.2102

Figure 1. Trajectories of $x_i(t)$, $i = 1, 2$, $u(t)$ and $y(t)$ for LF $|\mu| \leq 0.7$ range, (a) state $x_1(t)$, (b) state $x_2(t)$, (c) estimation controlled output $y(t)$, (d) estimation controlled output $u(t)$

5.2. Example 2

Let the fuzzy system (3) [25], where:

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} -1 & -1.155 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; A_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & -1.155 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; \\
 L_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} 1.4387 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}; L_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5613 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}; B_1 = B_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}; \\
 C_1 = C_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}; E_1 = E_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}; D_1 = D_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{34}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_2(x_1(t)) &= 0.5 - \frac{x_1^3(t)}{6.75}; \\
 N_1(x_1(t)) &= 1 - N_2(x_1(t)); x_1(t) \in (-1.5 \ 1.5)
 \end{aligned} \tag{35}$$

Figure 2. Trajectories of $x_i(t)$, $i = 1, 2$, $u(t)$ and $y(t)$ for MF $1 \leq |\mu| \leq 5$ range, (a) state $x_1(t)$, (b) state $x_2(t)$, (c) estimation controlled output $y(t)$, (d) estimation controlled output $u(t)$

Table 3. H_∞ performance bounds γ by different domains

Frequency ranges	methods	γ
$0 \leq \mu \leq \infty$	[16]	Infeasible
$0 \leq \mu \leq \infty$	Theorem 4.3. ($\tilde{S}_s = 0$)	1.4517
$ \mu \leq 628$	[16]	1.2215
$ \mu \leq 628$	Theorem 4.3.	0.7514
$628 \leq \mu \leq 6283$	[16]	1.025
$628 \leq \mu \leq 6283$	Theorem 4.3.	0.5274
$ \mu \geq 6283$	[16]	-
$ \mu \geq 6283$	Theorem 4.3.	0.3854

The FF case of $u(t)$ is assumed to satisfy 100 Hz; [100 1000] Hz and 1000 Hz, i.e., $|\mu| \leq 628$ rad/s; $628 \leq \mu \leq 6283$ rad/s; and $|\mu| \geq 6283$ rad/s, respectively for $u(t)$ and $\beta = 1$.

6. CONCLUSION

We sent the FF state feedback design. To reduce the closed-loop system and establish less conservative results, we have considered two practical examples has been provides to show the feasibility of tuning FF H_∞ fuzzy control design method.

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